

CRITICS: OPINIONS ABOUT JACK LONDON

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Annotation: This article is about the American Jack London, the founder of the genre known as science fiction. The article contains the most important information about Jack London, his life path, his works, and various opinions about the writer.

Keywords: Friedrich Nietzsche, Charles Darwin, Sigmund Freud, The Sea-Wolf, Martin Eden, Critics, Caleb Crain, novels, short stories, naturalism, romanticism

МНЕНИЯ КРИТИКОВ О ДЖЕКЕ ЛОНДОНЕ

Аннотация: Это статья об американце Джеке Лондоне, основоположнике жанра, известного как научная фантастика. В статье собраны самые важные сведения о Джеке Лондоне, его жизненном пути, творчестве, а также различные мнения о писателе.

Ключевые слова: Фридрих Ницше, Чарльз Дарвин, Зигмунд Фрейд, Морской волк, Мартин Иден, Критики, Калев Крейн, романы, рассказы, натурализм, романтизм.

JEK LONDON HAQIDA TANQIDLARCHILAR FIKRI

Annotatsiya: Bu ilmiy fantastika deb nomlanuvchi janr asoschisi amerikalik Jek London haqidagi maqola. Maqolada Jek London haqidagi eng muhim ma'lumotlar, uning hayot yo'li, ijodi, shuningdek, yozuvchi haqidagi turli fikrlar o'rin olgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Fridrix Nitsshe, Charlz Darvin, Zigmund Freyd, Dengiz bo'risi, Martin Iden, tanqidchilar, Kaleb Kren, romanlar, hikoyalar, naturalizm, romantizm.

INTRODUCTION

John Griffith Chaney (1876-1916), better known as Jack London, was an American novelist, journalist, and social activist. A pioneer of commercial fiction and American magazines, he was one of the first American authors to become an international celebrity and earn a large fortune from writing. He was also an innovator in the genre that would later become known as science fiction. The main reason Jack London became well-known as a writer was because of his ability to portray humanity's struggle in a hostile environment accurately. London came to the realization early in his career that he lacked the gift of creation and that, in writing, he would have to be an interpreter of the real world rather than a maker of imagined possibilities. He thus took inspiration for his stories, themes, characters, and settings from published narratives and real-life events. With the release of *A Daughter of the Snows* just after the turn of the 20th century, London's literary career got underway.

With the posthumous release of *The Assassination Bureau, Ltd.* In 1963, it came to a stop after nineteen novels. The lengths, subjects covered, and (most importantly) artistic quality of the novels vary greatly. London was able to write powerful short stories that were bold, violent, and occasionally primitive, portraying the frontier environment and the struggles of the people who lived there in a memorable way, but his novels frequently suffered from poor structure and overly didacticism.

Though it was never a major issue in his short stories, London's lack of inventiveness frequently showed up in his longer works. A handful of his books—*Burning Daylight*, for instance—have drawn criticism for being little more than collections of short stories bound together with the smallest amount of artistic license. The Canadian northland, where London started his literary apprenticeship; the archaic South Seas and Hawaii, where his career revived after a brief downturn; and the California wilderness, especially the Sonoma Valley, where London withdrew during his final years, are the three settings that London's novels most frequently feature.

MAIN BODY

Every novel also typically has a philosophical theme. Herbert Spencer's interpretation of Charles Darwin's theory of evolution, Friedrich Nietzsche's portrayal of the superman, and, much later, the new psychology of Sigmund Freud and Carl Jung, along with Karl Marx's conceptions of a new social order, were all popular at the period. All stoked London's creativity and gave him material for his characters and storylines; their existence, especially London's use of Darwin's "survival of the fittest" theme, validates London's claim to be a member of the naturalistic school of fiction.

Given the events of Jack London's brief but dramatic life, it seems appropriate that reviewers have focused on his biography almost since the beginning of his writing career.

In fact, he has been sensationalized so much in the past that readers have found it impossible to distinguish him from his fiction. While reading London's life, other academics have paid attention to the facts and how the biography might provide light on the fiction. However, they have found it difficult to shift the focus to London's contributions to American literature. London has moved from the periphery of American literary discourse to the center since the 1960s thanks to the scholarly foundations laid by Earle Labor, Sam S. Baskett, King Hendricks, Hensley C. Woodbridge, Earl J. Wilcox, and others, as well as a steady stream of critical and biographical works. There have been moments when this work has mirrored London's own pursuit of success.

What should critics do with an author who manifestly did not need them, who wrote for the masses but at the same time presented a set of complex personal, cultural, and artistic faces to the world? Although we are now in the postrecognition stage—that is, we no longer need to spend a lot of time explaining why London should be regarded as a major writer—London is still largely regarded in terms of the myths that surround him. While there has been a great deal of excellent criticism and biography, there is also a strong sense of how much more is needed. Newcomers to literary criticism on London are struck by two things: the range of his works and their artistic power. Many

had no idea of either until they moved past the handful of titles that made London famous—**The Call of the Wild** (1903), **White Fang** (1906), **The Sea-Wolf** (1904). Let's analyzed "The Sea- Wolf". The Sea-Wolf drew on London's youthful adventures in the sealing grounds off Japan.

The novel concerns the survival of upper-class Humphrey Van Weyden, a man who finds himself, by means beyond his control, aboard the Ghost, a weathered sailing ship. press on the way to Japan. Van Weyden soon discovers that the schooner's captain, Wolf Larsen, has created a hellish ship, filled with brutality and filth, where even the ship's actual purpose - seal hunting - are also lost in the misery of simple survival. Van Weyden survived in this environment because, like Buck, he was able to adapt to it, learn new rules of survival, rely on undiscovered instincts and make the best of all the advantages in his upbringing and status: intelligence, optimism and courage. loving capacity. Van Weyden's growth is the focus of the novel.

If Van Weyden survives because he, too, has learned the law of the club and the fang, the ship's captain, Wolf Larsen, dies precisely because he cannot adapt.

At least, that was London's intention, but it was lost upon many early critics. "I attacked Nietzsche and his super-man idea", London wrote to Mary Austin. "Lots of people read The Sea-Wolf, (but) no one discovered that it was an attack upon the super-man philosophy". The Sea-Wolf is a fine example of literary naturalism. Larsen, a sensitive, intelligent, domineering man, treats his crew with arrogance. He has no inhibitions and no friends. He is lonely and his life lacks purpose and direction. His loneliness and alienation from nature and people, and indeed, from himself, leads to his almost inevitable destruction. Without Van Weyden's adaptability, Larsen would have died.

If London fails to convince the reader that Larsen died because he was a superhero, it may be because London himself does not fully accept the idea. The world is full of superheroes - London sees himself as such in many ways - and the socialist alternative that London intellectually advocates is one that he cannot accept emotionally. This conflict between the ideas of Superman and socialism explodes fully

in Martin Eden, when London once again takes Nietzsche to task. The above is just a collection of short stories (more accessible than ever thanks to a handsome new edition). Novice critics were also puzzled by the conflicting accounts of London's life and values as a writer found in encyclopedias, anthology notes, and story.

As Susan Nuernberg observes in the introduction to her collection of critical essays on London, "The prevailing myths are that London was one of the most autobiographical of American writers, that he committed suicide, that he wrote obsessively about his illegitimacy, that he was a writer of dog stories and adventure tales for adolescent boys, that he was a racist, a womanizer, an alcoholic, and a hack writer, and that he contradicted himself and was confused in his thinking about socialism, individualism, scientific materialism, and idealism" (Critical Response xxiii). There is, of course, a grain of truth in any myth.

However, viewing London solely by the above description – as "a tangle of contradictions" (XXIII-XXIV) – leaves readers in the dark about such things as the reading and research he undertook to create the novel. His vision was essentially positive about his life and profession.

On the subject of his racism, like most thinkers of his time, London based his racist ideas on the scientific theories of the time, and this fact is clearly reflected clearly in his non-fiction essays on the subject. However, in his novels he delivered strong attacks against racism, especially in his short stories.

Regarding his personal life's shortcomings, we're impressed by his honesty with himself in questioning his behavior (such as drinking to excess) just as he had to do with his philosophical assumptions; and when examining London's physical health, one needs to.

Another critic, Caleb Crain, wrote his view of London: The ability to describe nature in a rich yet clear way of London foreshadowed Hemingway. He is at his best in the dog novels "The Call of the Wild" and "White Fang," perhaps because of more basic animal survival, perhaps because of a dog's love for the master for whom it worked escaped the master's shame.

But some of London's works have sought to integrate the life and death issues of the animal world into human issues, such as "To Build a Fire", the story of a man trying to avoid death by freezing. In "The Love of Life", a hungry man enjoys a meal like White Fang, and with equal enthusiasm: "There were four day-old chicks – tiny seeds of life thrilling, no more than one bite; and he ate them greedily, stuffing them alive into his mouth and cracking them like eggshells between his teeth". Even "Martin Eden", which takes place in the relatively civilized setting of San Francisco, vibrates with animal spirits. When the sailor Martin Eden first sees an oil painting, he dismisses it as a "trick picture", because the image seems to dissolve when he moves close enough to see the brushstrokes; there is an echo of White Fang's puppy snarl at the unfamiliar.

CONCLUSION

Although much more successful as a short-story writer than as a novelist, London's best novels remain alive and vibrant even to this day. His longer fiction was often episodic, disjointed, and loosely structured; his plots were often weak, and many times he let his characters preach rather than act out their philosophy.

Yet London offered a compelling vision of the human condition. The Darwinian struggle for survival was at the forefront of American thought in the early 20th century. London's novels reflect its society, including its contradictions, and lead readers into primordial arenas where the struggle for survival is at its finest. London's contribution to the naturalist tradition and his raw power as a storyteller ensured his continued place in the American literary legacy.

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